

Demonstration of Converged Metro+Access Bidirectional Transmission Using Coherent Transceivers and ROADMs

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Abstract: We present the experimental demonstration of high-speed transmission in downstream and upstream direction using off-the-shelf coherent transceivers in a 40-channel DWDM metro+access network configuration based on ROADMs for future all-optical metro-access converged solutions. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

ITU-T has recently published 50G-PON, the highest speed PON standard ratified so far, and has then opened a brainstorming in ITU-T SG15 towards G.suppl.VHSP “PON transmission technologies above 50 Gb/s per wavelength”. At the physical layer, the key debate is whether the next-gen PON will stick with intensity modulation and direct-detection (IM-DD) or if a new paradigm is needed, moving to PM-QAM and coherent (COH) detection.

In this paper, a broad extension of our previous works [1, 2], we investigate on some “added features” that a decision towards COH-PON would enable. In particular, thanks to COH better sensitivity and its resilience to chromatic dispersion vs. IM-DD, extended reach would be possible and thus metro+access all-optical convergence can be envisioned on the architecture shown in Fig. 1. Using DWDM and ROADM-based optical routing, this architecture would enable a seamless integration between metro and access segments, a reduction of the number of Optical-Electrical-Optical (OEO) conversions thanks to end-to-end optical lighthpaths and ultra-high capacity in the access, as it may be required by future fronthauling solutions for 6G [3] and/or new requirements coming from forthcoming edge AI applications. In the following, we present an experimental assessment on a deployed metropolitan fiber testbed of the resulting physical layer scalability at ultra high bit rates (200G and 400G net) in terms of PON Optical Distribution Network (ODN) loss, available metro OSNR and ROADM internal loss.

2. Network Architecture and Experimental Setup

We consider the general converged metro+access architecture shown in Fig. 1, and we experimentally demonstrate the part within the dark green dashed line, where a ROADM is placed at the boundary between the metro and PON sections to all-optically route the access wavelengths. Merging the metro and access transmission paradigms requires the upstream (US) and downstream (DS) lambdas to propagate along two different fibers in the metro part, and to share the same optical path on the access ODN.

The actual experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2: we used three 16.5 km fiber links deployed in the city of Turin, Italy, to connect the PhotoNext Lab at POLITO (where data streams are generated and detected), with the FiberCop lab (where a commercial ROADM has been installed). The used deployed fibers go trough several cabinets in the city of Turin, with many connectors generating spurious attenuation and back-reflections, as it is typical in access installations. Moreover, we used a standard $\Delta\lambda = 100$ GHz grid in the metro segment, and we routed a pair of wavelengths for the US and DS towards the access. Two commercial coherent transceivers are used to transmit and then detect the DS (black solid path) and US (red dotted path) modulated signals. We generated 200G PM-QPSK and 400G PM-16QAM streams at ≈ 63 GBaud, i.e. we focus on net data rates of 200Gbps and 400 Gbps. In the DS, one “access” signal at $\lambda_1 = 1558.17$ nm is combined with a WDM comb generated through an amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise source properly shaped through a Finisar 1000S Waveshaper to produce 38 dummy WDM channels spectrally located on channel slots from 16 to 55 of the ITU-T 100 GHz DWDM grid (as shown in the inset of Fig. 2). The full DS metro WDM comb is then amplified and coupled to ASE noise generated in a 200 GHz bandwidth around channel 24 (DS) and 25 (US) of the ITU-T grid through the traditional noise loading technique used to set the desired $OSNR_{METRO}^{DS}$ (defined on a bandwidth equal to the symbol rate) at the metro network input. We assume 10 channels (ch. 16 to 25) are used for the access and the

Fig. 1: General schematic of metro-access converged network (in dashed dark green, the actual experimental part, see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Experimental setup of the coherent metro-access network.

remaining 30 (ch. 26 to 55) for the metro traffic, as depicted in the dash-dot box in Fig. 2. In this way, the "access" λ s are conservatively allocated in EDFAs less performing bands, to favour the "metro-only" λ s. The total power at the $L_{METRO} = 16.5$ km fiber input is $P_{metro}^{DS} = 12$ dBm. The attenuation introduced by the metro fiber is about 15 dB. We used a commercial 4-degree ROADM, where each degree (i.e. each of the four possible directions) is made of an EDFA and a WSS. The DWDM comb traveling in DS is amplified inside the first degree (D1) through a pre-amplifier set to 22 dBm constant output power, to obtain 6 dBm power per λ at its output. The first WSS filters the 10-channel PON bundle and routes it towards D2 through a variable optical attenuator (VOA 3) used to vary the attenuation α_{OM} introduced in the ROADM internal connection matrix. In D2, another pre-amplifier is used to set the per- λ PON input power to 11 dBm, the typical highest value used in current PON standards. At the output of D2, the PON DS channel under test is filtered from the other PON λ s and sent (after a circulator) towards another $L_{PON} = 16.5$ km fiber emulating the access optical path. At the receiver input, VOA 4 is used to vary the received optical power (ROP) and set a given ODN loss α_{ODN} . In US direction, a circulator is used to transmit the US λ on the same PON fiber, with power $P_{PON}^{US} = 3.7$ dBm. At US PON output, the circulator sends the US $\lambda_2 = 1557.36$ nm on one port of the ROADM D2 WSS. The adjacent port is used to couple the other 9 dummy PON channels (re-routed from the DS bundle) and equalize them through VOA 5 to have comparable power to the US λ s under test. The D2 booster amplifier is set to 16 dBm constant output power to obtain 6 dBm per λ at VOA 6 input, used to set α_{OM} to the same values used in DS. At the D1 WSS, the PON bundle including the US λ s is multiplexed with the other 30 dummy metro λ s (again equalized by VOA 7 to get comparable powers per λ). The D1 booster amplifier is set to 16 dBm constant output power to have 0 dBm per λ at the metro link input. The whole 39-channel WDM comb then propagates along another $L_{METRO} = 16.5$ km fiber. At the receiver input, the signal is again coupled with ASE noise to set a desired $OSNR_{RX}^{US}$, amplified, filtered by a 100 GHz bandwidth optical filter and attenuated to set a ROP $P_{RX}^{US} = -7$ dBm.

Fig. 3: α_{ODN} in DS vs. $OSNR_{METRO}^{DS}$ for several values of α_{OM} at $BER_T = 10^{-3}$ (dotted), $BER_T = 10^{-2}$ (solid) and $BER_T = 2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (dashed) for a) 400G PM-16QAM and b) 200G PM-QPSK modulation. c) $\Delta OSNR_{RX}^{US}$ margin vs. α_{ODN} in US at $BER_T = 10^{-3}$ (black, star), $BER_T = 10^{-2}$ (red, square) and $BER_T = 2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ (blue, circle) for 400G PM-16QAM (solid) and 200G PM-QPSK (dashed).

3. Bidirectional Transmission Results

Both US and DS λ s are simultaneously transmitted to demonstrate 63 GBaud bidirectional communication on the metro+PON fiber deployed testbed, where flat (i.e. not angled) connectors are present inducing realistic in-field

reflections, which anyway did not cause any noticeable penalty in the system performance. To assess the resulting physical layer scalability, we experimentally measured the resulting end-to-end BER varying the following key metrics: i) the achievable PON α_{ODN} , ii) the attenuation α_{OM} of the ROADM switching matrix between WSSs and iii) the available $OSNR_{METRO}$ in each of the two directions. We would like to mention here that, even though (for hardware limitation in our lab) we used only one fiber span and one ROADM in the metro segment, we intentionally introduce ASE noise loading to obtain a wide range of $OSNR_{METRO}$ values (from 16 to 32 dB). We remind that for metro and long-haul transmission, the $OSNR$ (or actually its generalized G- $OSNR$ version that includes nonlinear GN-noise contribution) is today widely accepted as the key metric. The used 16 to 32 dB $OSNR_{METRO}$ range thus emulates generic metro network situations including several ROADMs and fiber spans.

At the receiver, we measure the BER as a function of ROP for several α_{ODN} values (imposed through VOA 4) and of the $OSNR$. Then, we compute the achievable α_{ODN} at different target $BER_T = 10^{-3}$, $BER_T = 10^{-2}$ and $BER_T = 2 \cdot 10^{-2}$ assuming three different FEC thresholds. Fig. 3a shows the DS α_{ODN} vs. $OSNR_{METRO}^{DS}$ for different α_{OM} (introduced through VOA 3) and 400G PM-16QAM (results at $BER_T = 10^{-3}$ could not be extracted due to the BER floor). At the lowest (highest) BER_T , very high 35 dB (33 dB) α_{ODN} can be obtained at the highest $OSNR_{METRO}^{DS} = 28$ dB and lowest $\alpha_{OM} = 4$ dB. Moreover, the impact of the attenuation associated with the optical matrix is only observable at very high α_{OM} values, above 24 dB, which largely exceeds the actual real maximum loss of possible ROADM internal connection matrix (including those based on optical splitters and switches). As a result, this attenuation does not have a significant impact on our results. In general, the $\alpha_{ODN} \geq 29$ dB required by the standards for instance for class N1 PON, can be easily provided in a 400G metro-access DS for $OSNR_{METRO}^{DS}$ levels above 23 dB and 18 dB in the extremely worst-case scenario with $\alpha_{OM} = 27$ dB at $BER_T = 10^{-2}$ and $BER_T = 2 \cdot 10^{-2}$, respectively. For the PM-QPSK DS case shown in Fig. 3b excellent α_{ODN} in excess of 40 dB is always possible at the two highest BER_T , even for very low $OSNR$ levels and high α_{OM} . In this case BER_T can also be lowered to 10^{-3} while still achieving $\alpha_{ODN} \geq 38$ dB. Please note that results shown in Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b include both circulators insertion loss (which are expected anyway to be less than 1 dB overall), that needs to be deducted for actual system performance evaluation. In the US direction, the power at the D2 booster amplifier input can be very low when α_{ODN} is high. The D1 booster amplifier also might receive a low power signal depending on the gain of the D2 booster and on optical matrix loss. Thus, the $OSNR_{RX}^{US}$ available at the receiver is imposed by the amplification stages inside the ROADM. Fig. 3c shows the metric $\Delta OSNR_{RX}^{US}$, defined here as the difference between the back-to-back $OSNR$ required at a given BER_T and the maximum $OSNR$ that can be obtained for any given α_{ODN} value in our US setup, i.e. as the $OSNR$ margin. The graph shows that $\Delta OSNR_{RX}^{US}$ reduces as expected as α_{ODN} increases, as the D2 booster has to amplify a progressively lower power signal. Nevertheless, even in the US direction, 200G PM-QPSK transmission is possible with $\alpha_{ODN} \geq 29$ dB for the considered BER_T and as high as 36.3 dB at $BER_T = 10^{-2}$, when the required $OSNR_{RX}^{US}$ is about 9 dB and 16 dB, respectively for the PM-QPSK and the PM-16QAM formats. The latter modulation at 400G net bit rate is more critical in US, enabling $\alpha_{ODN} \geq 29$ dB only at the highest considered FEC threshold with very low $OSNR$ margin.

4. Final comments

We have experimentally demonstrated coherent metro-access convergence capabilities in both DS and US direction using commercial optoelectronic hardware and installed fibers in the Turin (Italy) metro area. Our findings show that, for the typical target α_{ODN} in the PON and $OSNR$ in the metro, DS transmission can go as high as 400G net (using PM-16QAM) while US can reach 200G (PM-QPSK), in both cases with good system margins. We believe this paper gives a first general assessment on the feasibility of metro+PON convergence at ultra-high bit rates. Obviously, many issues are still open and requires a vast future research and development works. For sure, techno-economics will play a key role in the forthcoming decisions on what will be the next standard after 50G-PON. If coherent transmission is the selected option for PON, key open issues (not addressed in this paper) will be the multiplexing technology (which will likely require burst-mode coherent detection) and the wavelength allocation plan.

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